

**WETTING, FLUIDITY AND SOLIDIFICATION
IN
METAL MATRIX COMPOSITE CASTINGS:
A RESEARCH SUMMARY**

by

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes selected portions of a broad and continuing investigation at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology to investigate the solidification processing of metal matrix composites. The solidification process includes such fundamental issues as: (1) Wetting behavior at the interface between the infiltrating and solidifying molten metal and the ceramic reinforcement; (2) Fluid flow with accompanying solidification and macrosegregation and finally; (3) Solidification in the presence of the ceramic reinforcement.

This summary outlines the fundamental issues that must be addressed by that portion of the casting industries concerned with the development of solidification processing of Metal Matrix Composites.

INTRODUCTION

Over the past several years, the Solidification Processing Group has been broadened in scope and leadership to include metal matrix composite materials and its name has been changed to the "Solidification and Metal Matrix Composites Materials Group" which functions within the Center for the Processing and Evaluation of Metal and Ceramic Matrix Composites. Current work on composite materials in the group covers a wide spectrum including pressure infiltration, semi-solid slurry processing ("compocasting"), solidification of composites, interface science and tailoring, matrix microstructural design and optimization and physical and mechanical properties of metal matrix composites. Described herein is a portion of our current work at MIT involving solidification processing. Specifically, the research in progress toward doctorate dissertations of Messers. L. J. Masur and S-Y. Oh and the dissertations of Professor A. Mortensen and Dr. M.N. Gungor are summarized.

The casting process of a metal matrix composite is broken down into the stages of wetting, fluid flow and solidification as shown in Fig. 1. This sequence has been replicated in the organization of our research efforts as described below.

CERAMIC PARTICULATE WETTING by Al-ALLOYS (Mr. S-Y. Oh)

The wettability of the ceramic reinforcement with the molten matrix alloy is an important consideration since it affects the pressure requirements for infiltration, ease of dispersing ceramic particulate reinforcement, interface bond quality and the nature of defects in the resultant casting. In spite of the importance of wettability in solidification processing of

composites, relatively few studies have been conducted and many fundamental questions remain unanswered. This research is practically directed toward developing techniques for measuring the effects of surface treatments, alloy modifications and other important processing variables on the wettability of systems involving actual reinforcements used in metal matrix composites. The ultimate aim is to develop the fundamental understanding required for tailoring the reinforcement surfaces and alloys for effective processing of these composites into useful engineering materials.

An experimental technique for evaluation of wettability of ceramic particulates with liquid metal was developed. Wettability tests were conducted by pressure infiltration through uniformly packed powder specimens. The threshold pressures for infiltration can either be used as a quantitative measure of wettability or be converted to wetting angles by using the capillary force equation. With this technique, wettability was measured for SiC and B₄C particulates with unalloyed aluminum and Al-Cu and Al-Mg alloys. The effects of temperature, time, and alloying element on wettability were investigated. Other variables such as particle shape, surface treatment, and chemical composition as well as infiltration atmosphere are currently under investigation but not reported here.

Surface Energy and Wetting

The equilibrium configuration of a drop of liquid resting on a flat solid surface is determined by the liquid-vapor interfacial energy, γ_{lv} . The relationship between the surface energies of the system and the resulting wetting angle, θ , is shown in Fig. 2. The fundamental relationship is expressed by Young's equation (1)

$$\gamma_{sv} = \gamma_{sl} + \gamma_{lv} \cos \theta \quad (1)$$

Capillary rise is also related to surface energy balances and wetting phenomena. The height to which a liquid rises or is depressed depends on the capillary diameter, wetting angle and hence from equation (1), the balance of surface energies.

Considering the equilibrium of the raised liquid, capillary pressure, P_c , is given by

$$P_c = (2 \gamma_{lv} \cos \theta) / r \quad (2)$$

where r is the capillary radius and P_c can be from an applied pressure or from the hydrostatic pressure in the capillary of:

$$P_c = \rho g h \quad (3)$$

where ρ is the density of the liquid, g is the gravitational constant and h is the height of the liquid column. Fig. 3 shows wetting and non-wetting capillary systems.

Wettability is often defined as "the ability of a liquid to wet a solid surface, i.e., to give an even, continuous film over the solid surface..." [2]. In general, a system is called "wetting" when its contact angle, θ , is less than 90° and "non wetting" when θ is greater than 90°.

Methods of Measurement of Surface Energy and Wetting Angle

A number of techniques have been introduced to measure the surface energies and contact angles. The sessile drop method and maximum bubble pressure method are often used in wetting studies. The surface energies of solids have been measured by the zero-creep and multiphase equilibrium techniques. These techniques have been covered in several detailed reviews [3-9]. The factors that control wetting between ceramic solids and liquid metals include

heat of formation, valence electron concentration, interfacial reactions and kinetics of these reactions, surface geometry, temperature, and time. This subject has been discussed elsewhere [10, 11] by Russell, Oh, and Cornie. Approaches for theoretical estimation of surface energies are also considered in reference [11].

Experimental Approach

Filter resistance includes a breakthrough pressure required for infiltration. This threshold (breakthrough) pressure is the basic applied pressure required for the initiation of flow through a fibrous preform or packed bed. We utilized well qualified lots of SiC and B₄C grit (10 μm average dia) in these experiments. A packing device as shown in Fig. 4 was used to obtain uniform density packed bed into a 5 mm refractory coated quartz tube. When liquid is forced through the packed bed by an applied pressure, a threshold pressure is experienced before flow commences. This threshold pressure is measurable and can be related by equation 2. A device for measuring this threshold pressure is shown in Fig. 5. Specimens with a packing density of 52% ± 1.5% were isothermally infiltrated at a number of pressures. An extrapolation of the applied pressure vs infiltration distance relationship to zero infiltration length is a measurement of the threshold pressure. The threshold pressure is converted into contact angle θ values by replacing r in equation 2 with the hydraulic radius. (r_h = volume of liquid in the pore space divided by the wetted area).

Experimental Results

Infiltration Behavior - The infiltration distance is shown in Fig. 6 as a function of applied pressure for a SiC particulate/Al-2% Cu system in which the pressure was applied for 5 min at 900C. Each point represents the results of a separate experimental run. The linear relationship between applied pressure and infiltration distance is typical for SiC/Al alloy systems.

B₄C particulates, on the otherhand, interact with Al alloys differently as shown in Fig. 7 by the non linear infiltration distance vs applied pressure plot. The behavioral difference indicates different mechanisms of wetting.

Microstructure- Fig. 8 shows the microstructure of a SiC specimen preform infiltrated with pure Al at 700C for 5 min at 0.86 MPa (125 psi). Optical microscopy revealed a uniform appearing particle distribution with no evidence of redistribution during flow. Small voids at contact points between particles indicate non-infiltration into the narrowest regions of the packed bead. This phenomena was treated theoretically by Mortensen and Cornie[12].

A typical fracture surface of B₄C/Al-4.5% Cu infiltrated and solidified preform is shown in Fig. 9. This figure shows excellent bonding between the matrix and B₄C particles.

Effect of Temperature on Wettability- The contact angle in SiC/pure Al, SiC/2% Cu, and SiC/2% Mg composite systems is shown in Fig. 10 to decrease with increasing temperature, as expected. This effect may be partially thermodynamic due to changes in surface energies and partly kinetic due desorption and interfacial reactions. The rate of decrease in contact angle with increasing temperature is more reasonable than other experimental results for the Al/SiC system at the same temperature range [13] which showed little thermal effect. However, the rate of decrease on contact angle was not as high as that of other investigators for the Al₂O₃/ Al system [14].

Effect of Time on Wettability- The time dependence of the wetting angles in SiC/Al-alloy systems is shown in Fig. 11. Since several kinetic processes are involved in wetting, wetting angles decrease with time. Kinetic process include chemical reactions at the interface, dissolution of surface constituents into the melt, and adsorption at the surface. Wetting angles for the SiC/ Al-alloy systems changed very little after 5 min infiltration times.

Effect of Alloying Elements on Wettability- The change in wetting angle with addition of alloying elements is shown in Fig.12. Mg proved to be effective in decreasing the contact angle. On the other hand, additions of Cu to Al resulted in increased contact angles. Variables in wettability with alloying can be explained by changes in the surface energies, interfacial reactions, or in the electronic structures of surfaces.

Summary

The 5 min isochronal data for SiC/Al-alloy threshold pressure variation with applied pressure data is summarized in Table 1. Similar data for the B₄C/Al-alloy systems is displayed in Table 2. Also given in these tables are literature values for γ_{lv} , calculated values for θ and calculated or estimated ceramic surface-vapor and ceramic surface-liquid interfacial energies.

The mechanisms of wetting are not well understood even though several theories have been proposed. In reality, a given system can have one or more of several mechanisms operative. The main mechanisms proposed for wetting of ceramics with molten alloys are electronic charge transfer, dissolution, adsorption, and chemical reaction. These mechanisms are discussed at greater length in reference [11].

The wettability of ceramic particulates with molten Al alloys was measured by a new experimental technique. This technique enables a fast, accurate measurement of the effects of variables on the contact angle and as such, constitutes an effective means for fundamental as well as processing and materials optimization investigations. This is an active area of research at MIT.

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FLUIDITY IN METAL MATRIX COMPOSITE CASTINGS (Mr. L.J. Masur)

During the past few years the metal matrix composites (MMC) field has been experiencing a resurgence of interest, arising in part both from the current availability of several fibers with attractive properties and the development of fabrication methods with attractive economic factors. Attention in general has been focussed on reinforcing aluminum and its alloys, recognizing that there are other systems for future study. The attractive specific properties of MMC systems have been well documented, but the development of economically viable fabrication methods has limited their exploitation [1]. In the past, an industry has developed around the term "Premium Quality Castings" [2] which was based not upon trade secrets; but upon careful and specific control of processing parameters. These processing parameters were derived from a fundamental insight into the fundamental mechanisms involved in the solidification process. It is obvious that careful control of the processing parameters will be required to produce "Premium Quality Composite Castings". The development of the fundamental understanding of the infiltration process is the overall goal of this effort.

Much of the recent interest has centered around alumina fibers. Imperial Chemical Industries has developed a fine δ - Al_2O_3 fiber specifically aimed at MMC applications, known as "Saffil" RF grade [1]. The fiber is $3\mu\text{m}$ in diameter and for the purposes of MMC fabrication is chopped, milled and sized to give a preselected range of lengths. The δ - Al_2O_3 is stabilized against transformation to α - Al_2O_3 at elevated temperatures by the presence of 3% to 4% SiO_2 , which also tends to inhibit coarsening of the fiber crystallites. The work reported herein could equally be applied to other alumina-silicate fibers now being investigated and developed as metal reinforcement.

Clyne and Bader [3] recently studied the squeeze casting method of fabricating MMC's using "Saffil" fibers and both pure aluminum and Al-10% Mg matrices. Using measured experimental variables, they constructed a model of the processing sequence and predicted pressure and temperature distributions in the preform as well as a fiber packing density gradient due to preform deformation. Fukunaga and co-workers [4] infiltrated a devitroc ceramic fiber with pure aluminum using conventional die casting equipment. They found that when the metal or fiber temperatures were too low, or the infiltration pressure too low, then poorly infiltrated or very porous castings were produced. If the temperatures were too high, then excessive fiber/metal reaction caused poor castings. Finally, if the plunger speed was too fast then the preform was deformed upon infiltration.

Nagata and Matsuda wrote a series of papers studying particulate reinforced pure metals. Using squeeze casting techniques, they determined a critical preheating temperature (c.p.t.) of the preform, defined as the temperature above which the particles must be heated in order to completely infiltrate them [5,6,7].

Focussing on the infiltration process itself, Fukunaga and Goda [8] studied the infiltration length of pure aluminum in continuous glass fiber bundles. Using squeeze casting, they empirically found the relationship between infiltration length and squeeze pressure, fiber temperature and ram speed. They then constructed a model of the infiltration process based on the heat balance between the molten metal and the fiber bundle.

This work is aimed at understanding the infiltration of molten metal into a network of preheated fibers. The relationship between the infiltration behavior of molten metal and the processing conditions is of particular interest from two points of view: On an engineering

level, knowledge of the infiltration behavior of an alloy will enable an engineer to specify the temperatures and pressures necessary to infiltrate a given fiber preform. On a scientific level, an understanding of the relationship between infiltration length and processing parameters will elucidate the mechanism of the infiltration process, information which will then be used to improve the quality of cast composites.

The objective of this work is two-fold: We wish to understand both the effect of processing parameters on the infiltration behavior (fluidity), and the effect of processing parameters on the solidification behavior (macrosegregation). What follows is a summary of research-in-progress. Elsewhere in these proceedings is a more detailed analyses and modeling of the flow and solidification of pure metal into a packed fibrous preform [9].

Experimental Procedure

Experiments were performed by unidirectionally infiltrating Al - 4.5wt%Cu, a well-understood and well-behaved model alloy, into preforms of Saffil alumina fibers; the process is illustrated in Fig. 1. These experiments use nominal fiber packing densities of 18% and 24% by volume; the fibers are shown in Fig. 13.

Unidirectional infiltration of the Saffil preform is achieved with a new type of pressure casting machine, designated a hydrostatic pressure infiltration device (HPID). The operating principle behind the HPID is to use pressurized gas to force molten metal into an evacuated die. Fig. 14 is a schematic of the device. It consists of two main components: the pressure vessel, containing the melt furnace and crucible, and the cap, attached to which are the control valves and the die. There are also feedthroughs for thermocouples, power leads, and a pressure transducer. The die is attached to the center of the cap and can be evacuated.

To operate the device the cap is placed on the pressure vessel, immersing the bottom of the die in the molten metal. The vessel is then pressurized with nitrogen, forcing the metal up through the die and into the fibers. The metal and fibers do not come in contact until infiltration begins, which enables accurate and independent control of the fiber and metal temperatures. In addition, because of the design of the device the die need not sustain the load imposed by the pressurized metal, therefore heavy-walled metal dies common to other pressure casters are not necessary with this machine.

Used with the HPID is a technique developed to measure the position of the molten metal front as it moves through the fiber preform during infiltration. This is achieved by inserting a SiC filament between the preform and the quartz tube mold, Fig. 15. A potential is applied across the filament, using the molten metal as a switch to close the circuit. A chart recorder measures the potential drop across the SiC filament over time. As the metal infiltrates the preform the potential measured across the filament decreases due to the decrease of the effective electrical length of the SiC filament. Monitoring the potential drop over time allows a calculation of position and velocity over time.

To quantitatively measure macrosegregation in the cast composites, thin slices (1.5mm in thickness) were cut perpendicular to the metal infiltration direction at various locations along the length of the composite. The matrix material was then dissolved in a nitric acid/hydrochloric acid solution and separated from the fibers by filtration. The acid/alloy solution was then measured for copper concentration using atomic absorption spectroscopy.

Experimental Results

Fluidity- Work to date includes the investigation of the effect on composite length of infiltration pressure, fiber preheat temperature, metal superheat temperature and fiber volume fraction, each varied independently.

Parametric maps are displayed in Figs. 16A through 16D. The shape of the infiltration pressure curve indicates that composite length is very sensitive to pressure near the critical pressure threshold of approximately 0.5 MPa but becomes less sensitive to pressure at approximately 3-3.5 MPa. Conversely, the shape of the fiber preheat temperature curve indicates that composite length is increasingly sensitive to fiber preheat temperature as one increases from the critical threshold value of 350C. Metal superheat temperature has a much less pronounced, linear effect on length. Fiber volume fraction has a major effect on infiltration distance, but with only two fiber packing densities available it was not possible to fully evaluate the effect.

The effects of the three major processing parameters are summarized schematically in Fig. 17. The figure indicates that the effect on infiltration length of fiber preheat temperature is more significant than infiltration pressure which in turn is more significant than metal superheat temperature. Fiber packing density is, of course, the most significant of all the parameters.

Macrosegregation- Samples were evaluated for macrosegregation using the technique described above. The casting in the Fig. 18 shows a correlation between microstructure and composition. The porous region at the top of the casting is solute enriched and the pore-free region extending back towards the beginning of the fiber preform is solute impoverished. This macrosegregation is due to the transport of copper-enriched liquid (enriched due to the solidification of some of the flowing metal) from the base of the composite to the tip, as explained below.

As the molten metal infiltrates the cold preform, initially very small dendrites nucleate due to the cold fibers. These small grains are carried along by the flowing liquid metal and continue to grow as the metal is cooled. As the flowing liquid attempts to carry them downstream they become entrapped by the fiber network. Once trapped between fibers the small grains grow, and in doing so enrich the surrounding liquid with copper. The liquid is still able to flow and therefore carries the copper downstream to form a copper enriched area at the end of the composite. When the trapped grains grow to a size whereby they significantly block the flow of liquid downstream a large pressure drop results, which causes the porosity observed at the end of the composite. Finally the growing grains choke off fluid flow completely and infiltration ceases. The remaining liquid then solidifies and results in the structures shown.

Summary

1. An apparatus was developed for the unidirectional pressure infiltration into a fibrous preform under controlled processing conditions.
2. A technique was developed for monitoring the position of the liquid metal front in the preform during infiltration.
3. Processing maps were developed to relate the effect of fiber temperature, metal temperature, and infiltration pressure on infiltration length (fluidity).
4. Fiber preheat temperature was found to be more significant than infiltration pressure when alloy is cast at its liquidus temperature.
5. Macrosegregation occurs during infiltration into a cold preform.
6. The severity of the macrosegregation is a function of the temperature parameters.

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SOLIDIFICATION of an Al-4.5% Cu ALLOY AFTER INFILTRATION into CERAMIC FIBER PREFORMS (Prof. A. Mortensen and Dr. M.N. Gungor)

During solidification in the presence of fibers, dendrites grow so as to avoid fibers. The dendrite tip temperature is not significantly influenced by the fibers. However, the usual linear dependency of dendrite arm spacing on $t^{1/3}$ (where t is the solidification time) is altered significantly in the narrower interstices at long solidification times. The underlying mechanism is dendrite arm coalescence which takes place at a sufficiently rapid rate in the composite that the microstructure gradually becomes non-dendritic. The solid/liquid interface then contours the matrix/fiber interface.

The amount of microsegregation found within the inter-fiber spaces is significantly less than that found in a conventionally cast alloy, especially at long solidification times (low cooling rates). The underlying mechanism is solid-state diffusion which is enhanced in the composite by the fact that the fibers place an upper limit on the dendrite arm spacing and hence on the required diffusion distance.

Summary of Results

Dendritic Solidification in Metal Matrix Composites- It is possible to separate the problem of solidification during infiltration into a cold preform from that after infiltration by simply remelting a composite into a heated preform (above T_l) and resolidifying under controlled conditions. This was done in two recent doctoral theses in our group at MIT, both of which employed the model Al-4.5% Cu alloy [1,2].

In the first of these studies [1], the metal alloy was pressure infiltrated into preforms of SCS-2 (AVCO 140 μm diameter SiC) fibers. Small cylindrical composite specimens were then placed in a vertical Bridgman furnace, Fig. 19, and solidified at various controlled rates and gradients so that the local solidification time of portions of the samples solidified at steady state ranged from 4 s to 940 s. Most were abruptly quenched at a given time during solidification to reveal the dendritic structure; an example is shown in Fig. 20. The microstructures reveal, in one sample, dendrite arms where "local solidification time" varied from a very low value near the dendrite tip (because it was quenched soon after solidification began) to the "steady state local solidification time" t_f for the rate and gradient employed (at the point that was just solid at the time of quenching).

The dendrite tips in samples such as that shown in Fig. 20 all grow at temperatures very near the liquidus, as they do in the unreinforced alloy. Behind the tips, secondary arms form in all interstices. The spacings between the arms can be measured as a function of time t spent in the liquid solid region by simply measuring these spacings at increasing distance back from the tip. These spacings increase with increasing time in the liquid-solid region (local solidification time t). They do so as a result of coarsening, a surface tension driven phenomenon that reduces the total liquid/solid interfacial area. Coarsening is also observed in unreinforced castings, but it usually occurs more rapidly in the reinforced than in unreinforced castings. Results of measurements on a sample which had a steady state local solidification time of 268 seconds are shown in Fig. 21. Data shown in this figure are for dendrite arms in the interstices between three closely spaced 140 μm fibers, while the straight line gives the

standard $t^{1/3}$ relationship between dendrite arm spacing and local solidification time for the unreinforced alloy under steady state solidification.

A remarkable phenomenon is seen in Fig. 21 which is less than a third of the steady state solidification time t_f of this sample. Dendrite arms are no longer visible at all; they have totally disappeared during the solidification process. This is something that never occurs in usual castings and ingots, regardless of how slow the cooling is. In usual castings and ingots, secondary dendrite arms grow progressively during most of solidification by a process of coarsening that is termed "ripening". Small arms tend to re-melt while large ones grow. The driving force is surface energy, and mass transport is by diffusion through the liquid. This process has been studied by a large number of investigators, several of whom have developed quantitative treatments for the ripening process [11,12]. These treatments all give, in one form or another, the standard relationship of dendrite arm spacing to local solidification time, t_f , or to cooling rate, c :

$$d = A [t_f]^{1/3} \quad (1)$$

$$d = B[c]^{-1/3} \quad (2)$$

The first of these relationships is plotted as the solid line of Fig. 21. This process is shown schematically in Fig. 22.

Toward the end of solidification at high volume fractions solid, a different coarsening method becomes operative; i.e. a different mechanism operates to reduce liquid-solid surface area of the solidifying alloy. That mechanism is "coalescence" whereby interdendritic regions "fill in" with solute, again with mass transport by diffusion through the liquid. In usual castings and ingots, this mechanism accounts for the "platelike" dendritic structures often seen, but it never results in elimination of the dendrite structure itself. The mechanism is shown schematically in Fig. 23, and Figs. 24a and 24b show how the two mechanisms combine to produce solidification structures observed, for the case of directionally solidified monolithic and composite castings respectively.

Coalescence was further studied in the doctoral thesis work of M. Gungor [2], in which the Al-4.5% Cu alloy was infiltrated into preforms of fine alumina fibers, 20 μm diameter (Du Pont "FP" fibers). In these experiments, the infiltrated composites were re-melted and re-solidified at known cooling rates with very low temperature gradients, and then quenched at various times during solidification. Thus, the structure within a given sample was uniform throughout the sample and greater statistical data could be obtained on dendrite arm spacing. Results are shown in Fig. 25. Whether or not the dendrites actually disappear by coalescence in a given situation depends on cooling rate and fiber spacing. Here, for a fixed average fiber spacing, as the solidification time t_f increases (or conversely as the cooling rate decreases), the dendritic microstructure is eliminated. This process is evident in Fig. 25. As the cooling rate decreases and, hence, the solidification time t_f increases, secondary dendrite arms become fewer and less well-defined. In a sample solidified in 750 seconds, the matrix has had time to "erase" nearly all dendrite arms, and the microstructure is thus essentially non-dendritic.

We have treated the foregoing coalescence problem quantitatively, and have obtained good agreement of theory with experiment in relating the critical time for disappearance of dendrites, t_c with steady state solidification time, t_f , and with geometric parameters of SiC reinforced Al-4.5% Cu matrix composites(1). A comparison of theory with experiment is given in Fig. 26.

In the alumina reinforced composites, the kinetics of dendrite arm coarsening were also accelerated by the fibers (as shown in Fig. 27). Instead of the usual relationship for castings ($t^{1/3}$), the secondary arm spacing varied as:

$$\lambda_2 = 9.7 t_f^{0.51} \quad (3)$$

With only slight dependence on fiber volume fraction Fig. 26. A greater fiber volume fraction dependence would be expected for composites with a more uniform fiber distribution.

Microsegregation- Coalescence modifies the morphology of the solidified matrix microstructure, but does not decrease "coring" in the solid metal measured by minimum composition observed at the center of dendrites, nor does it result in full elimination of eutectic in the structure. These can be achieved only by diffusion in the solid during and after solidification. Homogeneity, as measured by these factors, is much greater in the composite than in usual castings and ingots, as shown by the data of Fig. 28. At the longer solidification times, homogenization is virtually complete, with the minimum composition measured in the metal matrix approaching the maximum overall composition of 4.5% Cu. This result also follows directly from the restraint of the fibers on the dendrite size. The reduced dendrite spacing increases the critical dimensionless parameter for diffusion, Dt/d^2 , where D is the solid diffusion coefficient, t is time and d is dendrite arm spacing. Here, at the same diffusion time t , the extent of diffusion is greater in the composite. This process was modeled for Al-4.5% Cu reinforced with SiC fibers, and results from calculations agreed with experiment, indicating that solid state diffusion is indeed responsible for the observation.

CONCLUSION

Investigators in many laboratories throughout the world are studying metal-matrix composite materials and engineering applications for these materials. Results of work presented herein show that control of solidification of such composites can produce matrices that are much more homogeneous than usual cast materials. Thus the designer is provided a new and potentially important tool for tailoring optimum properties in his composite.

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Table I. Threshold pressure, surface energy, wetting angle, and work of immersion for SiC/Al alloy systems.

Alloy	Temp.(°C)	P_{th} (psi) ^{a)}	γ_{lv} (erg/cm ²) ^{b)}	θ ^{c)}	γ_{sv} ^{d)}	γ_{sl} ^{e)}	W_i ^{f)}
Pure Al	700	133	851	124.3	2469	2949	-480
	800	99.5	840	115.3	2414	2773	-359
	900	90	830	113.0	2360	2684	-324
Al-2% Cu	700	135.5	843	125.4	2469	2957	-488
	800	110	832	118.5	2414	2811	-397
	900	81	822	110.8	2360	2652	-292
Al-4.5% Cu	800	104	831	116.8	2414	2789	-375
Al-2% Mg	700	108	767	120.5	2469	2858	-389
	800	82	757	113.0	2414	2710	-296
	900	67	747	108.9	2360	2602	-242
Al-4.5% Mg	800	76	652	114.8	2414	2687	-275

a) present experimental result

b) from ref. [26]

c) calculated from P_{th}

d) calculated by using eq.(34)

e) calculated by using eq.(1)

f) calculated by using eq.(6)

Table II. Threshold pressure, surface energy, and wetting angle for B₄C/Al-alloy systems.

Alloy	Temp.(°C)	P _{th} (psi) ^{a)}	γ _{lv} (erg/cm ²) ^{b)}	θ ^{c)}
Pure Al	700	116	851	120.0
	800	109	840	115.6
	900	83	830	109.4
Al-2% Cu	700	114	843	116.7
	800	103	832	114.3
	900	85	822	110.1
Al-4.5% Cu	800	97	831	112.9
Al-2% Mg	700	98	767	115.1
	800	35	757	98.9
	900	20	747	95.1
Al-4.5% Mg	800	10	652	92.9

a) present experimental result

b) from ref.[26]

c) calculated from P_{th}

Fig. 1: Schematic of the unidirectional infiltration process. Molten metal at temperature T_M is infiltrated into a fiber preform at temperature T_F under an infiltration pressure P . The result is a composite of length L .

$$\Delta P = \frac{2\gamma_{lv} \cos \theta}{r} = \rho g h$$

Wetting equilibrium

Young's equation

$$\gamma_{sv} = \gamma_{sl} + \gamma_{lv} \cos \theta$$

Fig. 2. Schematic diagram of a liquid drop on the solid surface showing the interfacial forces and wetting angle for wetting and non-wetting systems, respectively.

Fig. 3. Wetting and non-wetting capillary systems.

Fig. 4. Sketch of tamping device.

Fig. 5. Sketch of pressure chamber.

Fig. 6. Variation of the infiltration distance as a function of applied pressure for SiC/Al-2% Cu system at 900 C.

Fig. 7. Variation of the infiltration distance as a function of applied pressure for B₄C/Al-4.5% Mg system at 800 C.

Fig. 8. Microstructure of SiC powder specimen infiltrated with pure aluminum with 125 psi at 800C.

Fig. 9. Fracture surfaces of B₄C specimen infiltrated with Al-4.5% Cu with 105 psi at 800 C.

Fig. 10. Change in wetting angle with temperature for SiC/Al-alloy systems.

Fig. 11. Change in wetting angle with time for SiC/Al-alloy systems at 800°C.

Fig. 12. Change in wetting angle with alloying element for SiC/Al-alloy systems at 800°C.

Fig. 13. SEM micrograph of Saffil alumina fiber preform. Infiltration direction is parallel to viewing direction.

Fig 14. Schematic of Hydrostatic pressure infiltration device.

Fig. 15. Schematic of device for measuring position of molten metal front during infiltration.

Fig. 16. Parametric maps showing effect of processing parameters on infiltration length. A: infiltration pressure, B: fiber preheat temperature

Fig 16., cont. C: metal superheat temperature, D: fiber volume fraction.

PARAMETER SUMMARY

Fig. 17. Schematic summary of the effect of Processing parameters on infiltration length. A steeper slope denotes a more significant effect.

Fig. 18. Illustration of macrosegregation resulting from infiltration of molten alloy into a cold fiber preform. Copper concentration increases in the porous region of the casting, resulting in a microstructure enriched in eutectic. Sound portion of casting is solute-impooverished.

Fig. 19. Bridgman furnace for steady state solidification experiments.

Fig. 20. Dendrites, growing in a large interstice (right) and a small interstice (left). The dendrite in the center interstice intersects the plane of polish only near the bottom of the figure.

Fig. 21. Experimental points for secondary dendrite arm spacing versus local solidification time for a small interstice between three close packed SiC fibers 140 microns in diameter. Steady state solidification time t_f for the sample was 268 seconds.

Fig. 22. Ripening mechanisms for secondary dendrite arms.

Fig. 23. Coalescence mechanisms for secondary dendrite arms.

Fig. 24. Schematic diagram of four stages during dendritic growth of Al-4.5wt%Cu alloy in a fiber-free alloy (left) and between fibers (right).

Fig. 25. Microstructural evolution of Al-4.5wt%Cu reinforced with continuous alumina fibers 20 microns in diameter as the solidification time t_f varies from A) 1.3 s to B) 18s; C) 192s and D) 750s. It can be noted that the microstructure gradually becomes less dendritic as the solidification time increases.

Fig. 25.

Fig. 26. Comparison of measured and predicted time for complete coalescence of secondary dendrite arms in Al-4.5wt%Cu reinforced with SiC fibers 140 microns in diameter. Experiments and calculations are for interstices between close packed fibers, and between touching fibers in a square array.

Fig. 27. Secondary dendrite arm spacing versus solidification time t_f for usual castings and ingots and for Al-4.5wt%Cu reinforced with alumina fibers 20 microns in diameter.

Fig. 28. Minimum copper concentration in fiber-free Al-4.5wt%Cu and Al-4.5wt%Cu reinforced with alumina fibers as a function of the solidification time t_f .

